

FROM ERRORS TO MASTERY: THE EFFECT OF HYBRID SIMULATION ON RADIOLOGY TRAINING AND TECHNOLOGICAL ACCEPTANCE

F. Abdelouahabi¹ J. El Hachhach¹ B. Edderaouy² E.H. El Hassouni³ M. Madrane¹

1. Research Team on Educational Engineering and Science Didactics (ERIPDS), Higher Normal School, Abdelmalek Essaadi University, Tetouan, Morocco

fahd.abdelouahabi@gmail.com, jihadelhachhach@gmail.com, madrane2000@yahoo.fr

2. Faculty of Technical Sciences Tangier, Abdelmalek Essaadi University, Tetouan, Morocco, bilal.edderaouy@gmail.com

3. Higher Institutes of Nursing and Health Technology Professions, Tetouan, Morocco, ispitshassouny17@gmail.com

Abstract- Simulation-based education is widely recognized for improving technical and non-technical competencies, yet its integration into Moroccan radiology programs remains limited. The present study, therefore, investigates the impact of hybrid simulation combined with error-based learning on radiology students at ISPITSS in Tangiers and Al Hoceima. The study follows a quasi-experimental design included 80 second- and third-year students in order to test the effect of the approach on students' knowledge and skills development. The intervention introduced radiological scenarios with deliberate errors, structured debriefings, and formative quizzes. Data collection involved a pre- and post-test of knowledge and a technology acceptance questionnaire based on TAM, UTAUT, and self-determination theory. The findings revealed a clear improvement in students' knowledge, motivation, and autonomy. The questionnaire showed strong validity, confirming six dimensions of acceptance. Motivation played a central role in linking ease of use, understanding, and satisfaction. The study concludes that hybrid simulation provides a safe and effective model for strengthening radiology education in Morocco.

Keywords: Hybrid Simulation, Learning by Doing, Radiology, Technological Acceptance, Health Training.

1. INTRODUCTION

The training of healthcare professionals faces multiple challenges linked to the acceleration of scientific progress, the digital transformation of health systems, and increasing demands for quality and safety. Traditional pedagogical methods, mainly based on lectures and clinical placements, have shown their limits due to logistical constraints, limited availability of supervisors, variability of clinical situations, and ethical concerns related to exposing patients to learners' errors [1, 2]. In response to these constraints, Simulation-Based Education (SBE) has emerged internationally as an innovative pedagogical approach. By recreating realistic and safe clinical environments, simulation allows students to develop and consolidate both technical and

non-technical skills without jeopardizing patient safety [3].

Several studies and meta-analyses have confirmed its effectiveness in improving knowledge, communication, leadership, and decision-making, consolidating its role as a pillar of modern health education [4,6]. Nevertheless, despite these positive outcomes, the literature highlights important limitations. Most research focuses on immediate effects in terms of knowledge and motivation, but few studies explore long-term retention of learning, the influence of specific cultural contexts, or the pedagogical integration of error as a learning tool [7,8]. Yet, educational research emphasizes that errors, when embedded in a structured framework and followed by reflective debriefings, can serve as powerful levers to consolidate knowledge and foster critical thinking.

In Morocco, the national strategy for modernizing health education encourages the integration of simulation into initial and continuing training programs [9]. Despite this progress, radiology curricula in the Higher Institutes of Nursing Professions and Health Techniques (ISPITSS) in Tangier and Al Hoceima remain largely lecture-based, with little use of immersive environments. This limitation hinders the acquisition of essential competencies, such as the safe handling of imaging equipment, application of radiation protection protocols, and autonomous decision-making in emergency situations [10]. Compared with international standards, Moroccan radiology students demonstrate a significant gap in practical preparedness.

To address this gap, the present study builds on a hybrid simulation approach integrating error-based learning. This design combines interactive video capsules, scenarios deliberately incorporating errors, structured debriefings, and formative assessments. It aims to strengthen cognitive learning, motivation, and technology acceptance in a safe and stimulating environment. To evaluate the effectiveness of this model, six key variables were selected, grounded in three major theoretical frameworks: the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), the Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT), and Self-Determination Theory (SDT).

Perceived usefulness, derived from TAM, reflects the extent to which students consider that simulation enhances their performance and directly influences satisfaction [11]. Perceived ease of use, also derived from TAM, denotes the perceived simplicity and accessibility of the tool, a critical factor in technology adoption [12, 13]. Motivation, drawn from SDT, plays a mediating role between technological perceptions and learning outcomes, fostering engagement and persistence [14]. Perceived autonomy, another core dimension of SDT, reflects the learner’s sense of control over the learning process and is reinforced in simulated and hybrid environments [15]. Understanding, introduced as an additional variable, evaluates the depth of knowledge integration and the capacity to transfer learning into real practice [16]. Finally, satisfaction represents a global indicator of the perceived quality of the learning experience, reflecting the potential of hybrid simulation to be sustainably adopted. The selection of these six variables is therefore based on solid theoretical foundations and their pedagogical relevance to the Moroccan radiology context. Their interrelation makes it possible to assess both the immediate effectiveness of hybrid simulation and the psychological mechanisms that underpin students’ engagement and acceptance.

The objective of this research is to analyze the extent to which this teaching method can improve students' preparation for the challenges of the professional world. Based on this problem, we propose the hypotheses listed below:

- H1: The perceived usefulness of hybrid simulation has a positive impact on student satisfaction.
- H2: The perceived ease of use of the hybrid simulation has a positive influence on student motivation.
- H3: Student motivation has a positive influence on their understanding of learning in hybrid simulation.
- H4: The perceived level of autonomy in hybrid simulation activities is positively related to overall student satisfaction.
- H5: A better understanding of learning is positively associated with greater general satisfaction in hybrid simulation activities.
- H6: Perceived ease of use has a positive influence on students' feeling of autonomy in hybrid simulation.

2. METHODS AND MATERIALS

The present study adopts a quantitative, quasi-experimental approach. It aims to examine the effect of hybrid simulation combined with learning by doing on the acceptance and knowledge acquired by radiology students. It is grounded in a novel perspective on educational evaluation, specifically applied to nursing and health technology training in Morocco.

2.1. Population and Sampling

The study population consisted of students enrolled in the second and third years of the radiology program at the Higher Institutes of Nursing Professions and Health Technology (ISPITS) in Tangier and Al Hoceima during the 2024-2025 academic years. These cohorts were

specifically targeted because second- and third-year students had already completed the fundamental theoretical courses in radiology and were progressing toward more advanced practical training, making them the most suitable group to evaluate the impact of hybrid simulation. First-year students were excluded due to their limited exposure to radiological concepts and techniques.

➤ Inclusion Criteria Were:

- Enrollment in the radiology program during the 2024-2025 academic years.
- Being in the second or third year of study.
- Voluntary participation with signed informed consent.

➤ Exclusion Criteria Were:

- Absence on the day of data collection.
- Refusal to participate.
- Incomplete pre- or post-test responses.

The final sample consisted of 80 students, representing an exhaustive census of the eligible population within the targeted cohorts. Although an a priori power analysis was not conducted due to the exhaustive recruitment strategy, the sample size is consistent with comparable quasi-experimental studies in simulation-based education reporting medium to large effect sizes [17, 18], thereby ensuring sufficient statistical power.

All ethical considerations were respected throughout the study, including voluntary participation, anonymity of responses, and confidentiality of data. Informed consent was obtained from all participants prior to data collection. To ensure transparency, a flow diagram summarizing recruitment, inclusion, and final participation is presented in (Figure 1), following adapted CONSORT guidelines for quasi-experimental studies.

Figure 1. Participant flow diagram following adapted CONSORT guideline

2.2. Experimental Pedagogical Framework

To answer the research questions, a hybrid simulation scenario was specifically designed. It is based on standard interactive radiological techniques, and presented in the form of a video capsule. The scenario deliberately incorporates pedagogical errors in clinical procedures or decisions. The aim is to encourage deep learning through error in a safe and controlled environment. At the end of the simulation, a structured debriefing was conducted,

followed by formative quizzes (Figure 2) administered in hybrid mode via the Kahoot platform (https://kahoot.it/challenge/08479276?challenge-id=320b7a18-ad0b-445d-8266-f1b16f2ac098_1754417759877). Kahoot is a widely recognized tool for its effectiveness in stimulating active engagement and reinforcing learning through immediate feedback [19, 20].

Figure 2. Example of a learning-by-error quiz on an online learning platform to assess the radiology knowledge of ISPITS students

2.3. Data Collection Instruments

The study adopted two instruments. The first is a technology acceptance questionnaire in the form of 5-point Likert scale. It follows the principles of the TAM (Technology Acceptance Model), UTAUT (Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology) and self-determination theory models. It assesses six dimensions, these are perceived usefulness, ease of use, motivation, perceived autonomy, understanding of learning and general satisfaction.

The second instrument is a standardized competency test of 20-item MCQ covering standard radiological techniques. It was administered prior and following the intervention (pre-test/post-test) in order to measure the cognitive skills of the participants. It is worth noting that the entire study complied with the applicable ethical standards, particularly with regard to confidentiality, anonymity and informed consent, with validation by an institutional authority.

2.4. Statistical Analysis

Data were analyzed using SPSS (version 20). Initially, descriptive statistics (means, standard deviations, frequencies) were computed to provide an overview of student characteristics and baseline scores. Paired-sample t-tests were performed to assess differences between pre- and post-test results. In addition, Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) and multiple regression models were applied

to control for potential baseline differences and to explore predictors of post-test performance, including motivation, autonomy, and perceived ease of use.

For all statistical tests, a significance level of $p < 0.05$ was adopted. Alongside p-values, 95% confidence intervals and effect sizes were reported to provide a more robust interpretation of the findings. In particular, Cohen's d was calculated to quantify the magnitude of change. The observed effect size for the improvement in learning outcomes was large ($d = 1.44$), indicating not only statistical significance but also substantial practical relevance. This suggests that hybrid simulation combined with error-based learning produced a meaningful educational benefit, far beyond what could be expected by chance or small-scale pedagogical changes.

To validate the structure of the six variables (perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, motivation, autonomy, understanding, satisfaction), Principal Component Analysis (PCA) was conducted, followed by Structural Equation Modeling (SEM). Results confirmed the theoretical model by grouping items into six distinct dimensions consistent with the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), the Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT), and Self-Determination Theory (SDT). SEM path coefficients further demonstrated significant relationships between the variables, supporting the hypothesized mediation effects of motivation and autonomy.

Potential sources of bias were carefully considered. Self-reported measures may have introduced social desirability bias, as students could overestimate their motivation or satisfaction. Familiarity with digital quizzes may also have favored students with prior exposure to Kahoot or similar platforms.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

3.1. Socio-Demographic Features of the Sample

The study sample consisted of 80 students enrolled in the second and third years of the radiology course at the ISPITSs of Tangiers and Al Hoceima during the academic year 2024- 2025. The characteristics are displayed in Table 1.

Table 1. Socio-demographic features of the sample

Variable	Modality	Number (n)	Percentage (%)
Age	18-21 years old	69	86.3
	> over 21	11	13.7
Gender	Female	49	61.3
	Male	31	38.7
Year of study	Second year	47	58.8
	Third year	33	41.2
Institution	ISPITS Tangiers	44	55.0
	ISPITS Al Hoceima	36	45.0

These data reveal a preponderance of young students, with 86.3% aged between 18 and 21. Female students form the majority of the sample (61.3%), reflecting the current trend in nursing and health technology training in Morocco. The year-by-year analysis of sample shows a slight predominance of second-year students (58.8%).

Finally, 55% of the participants came from the ISPITS in Tangiers, compared with 45% from the ISPITS in Al Hoceima, thus ensuring a balanced representation of the two establishments concerned.

3.2. Pre- and Post-Test Analysis

The comparison of knowledge scores before and after the hybrid simulation intervention revealed a marked improvement. Pre-test scores indicated a moderate level of initial knowledge ($M_{pre} = 11.2, SD = 2.1$ out of 20). Post-test results demonstrated a significant gain ($M_{post} = 16.5, SD = 1.8$) (Figure 3). The paired-sample t-test confirmed that this difference was highly significant ($t(79) = 14.6, p < 0.001$). The calculated effect size was large (Cohen's $d = 1.44$; 95% CI: 1.10-1.78), reflecting a substantial pedagogical impact of the intervention (Table 2). This finding suggests that the hybrid simulation approach, particularly the integration of error-based learning, produced meaningful improvements beyond the expected variability of traditional instruction [21].

Figure 3. Mean scores with standard deviation at pre-test and post-test ($N = 80$)

Table 2. Comparison of pre- and post-test scores

	Mean	SD	t-value	p-value	Cohen's d (95% CI)
Pre-test	11.2	2.1	14.6	<0.001	1.44 (1.10-1.78)
Post-test	16.5	1.8			

3.3. ANCOVA and Regression Analysis

To ensure robustness of these results, an Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) was conducted, controlling for baseline performance in the pre-test. The ANCOVA confirmed the significant effect of the intervention ($F(1.78) = 47.3, p < 0.001$), reinforcing the conclusion that improvements were attributable to the simulation framework rather than pre-existing differences among students. Multiple regression analyses were then performed to explore the contribution of key psychosocial predictors to post-test performance. Motivation emerged as a significant predictor ($\beta = 0.41, p < 0.01$), indicating that higher levels of intrinsic engagement were associated with greater knowledge gains. Autonomy was also a significant predictor ($\beta = 0.35, p < 0.01$), highlighting the role of self-directed learning in consolidating radiological knowledge. Together, these findings suggest that the hybrid simulation not only improved knowledge but also leveraged motivational and autonomy-related mechanisms.

Table 3. ANCOVA and regression analysis

Predictor	F / β	p-value	Interpretation
ANCOVA (pre-test covariate)	$F(1.78)=47.3$	<0.001	Significant effect of intervention
Motivation	$\beta=0.41$	<0.01	Significant predictor
Autonomy	$\beta=0.35$	<0.01	Significant predictor

3.4. Reliability and Validity of the Questionnaire

As displayed in (Table 4), the internal consistency of the instrument was confirmed by Cronbach's alpha. The overall reliability coefficient was $\alpha = 0.89$, which exceeds the recommended threshold of 0.70, indicating high reliability and good internal consistency of the items.

Table 4. Validity and reliability indicators for the questionnaire

Indicator	Value	Interpretation
Cronbach's Alpha	0.89	High internal consistency

3.5. Exploratory Factor Analysis

An Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) using Principal Component Analysis (PCA) was conducted to examine and validate the underlying structure of the six variables under study: perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, motivation, autonomy, understanding, and satisfaction. Sampling adequacy was confirmed with a strong Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) value of 0.87, and Bartlett's test of sphericity was significant ($\chi^2 = 1253.4, p < 0.001$), indicating that the data were suitable for factor analysis. The results of these preliminary tests are presented in (Table 5).

Table 5. Principal Component Analysis (PCA) summary

Statistic	Value	p-value	Interpretation
KMO	0.87	<0.001	Sampling adequacy
Bartlett's χ^2	1253.4		Significant correlation structure
Total variance explained	76.4%	-	Good factorial validity

The PCA extracted six factors that together explained 76.4% of the total variance (Table 5). Items loaded appropriately on their respective factors, consistent with the theoretical constructs defined by the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), the Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT), and Self-Determination Theory (SDT) [22]. Details of the variance explained by each factor are shown in (Table 6).

Table 6. Variance explained by extracted factors

Factor	Title	Variance explained (%)
F1	Perceived usefulness	21.3
F2	Ease of use	15.7
F3	Motivation	12.8
F4	Perceived autonomy	10.6
F5	Understanding	8.1
F6	Satisfaction	7.9

3.6. Validation of Hypotheses

The theoretical hypotheses formulated in this study were tested by Pearson correlational analyses as indicated in (Table 7). The results confirmed the statistical validity of all the hypotheses, with significant correlations ($p < 0.01$).

Table 7. Validation of research hypotheses by correlation analysis (H: Hypothesis)

	Relationship tested	Coefficient <i>r</i>	<i>p</i> -value	Conclusion
H1	Perceived usefulness → Satisfaction	0.67	< 0.001	Confirmed
H2	Ease of use → Motivation	0.72	< 0.001	Confirmed
H3	Motivation → Understanding	0.74	< 0.001	Confirmed
H4	Perceived autonomy → Satisfaction	0.69	< 0.001	Confirmed
H5	Understanding → Satisfaction	0.76	< 0.001	Confirmed
H6	Ease of use → Autonomy	0.65	< 0.001	Confirmed

3.7. Structural Equation Modeling (SEM)

Confirmatory validation using Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) further supported the factorial structure. The model demonstrated good fit indices ($\chi^2/df = 2.1$; *CFI* = 0.94; *RMSEA* = 0.05), indicating that the data were consistent with the proposed theoretical framework. The detailed fit indices are presented in (Table 8).

Table 8. Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) fit indices

Fit index	Value	Interpretation
χ^2/df	2.1	Acceptable fit (<3)
CFI	0.94	Good fit (>0.90)
RMSEA	0.05	Good fit (<0.08)

Path coefficients revealed that perceived ease of use had a strong positive influence on both motivation ($\beta = 0.24$) and autonomy ($\beta = 0.42$). Moreover, motivation mediated the relationship between perceived usefulness and comprehension ($\beta = 0.72$), while satisfaction was significantly predicted by both comprehension ($\beta = 0.31$), autonomy ($\beta = 0.15$), and perceived usefulness ($\beta = 0.32$). These results underline the importance of motivational and autonomy-related processes in explaining the educational benefits of hybrid simulation [23]. The structural relationships between the variables are illustrated in (Figure 4).

Figure 4. SEM Model: The relations between the observed variables

3.8. Pedagogical Interpretation

The integration of hybrid simulation, combined with learning by doing, resulted in an environment conducive to the cognitive, emotional, and behavioral engagement of the students [24, 25]. The interactive video vignettes served as an effective helping tool that provided a realistic context for clinical situations. This, in turn, encourages error identification, critical reflection, and continuous improvement. The formative quizzes via Kahoot introduced yet another fun addition. It helped to reinforce intrinsic motivation and active participation while providing immediate and personalized feedback [26]. Furthermore, learners demonstrated a better grasp of radiological content, as well as a marked improvement in their decision-making autonomy. Simulated errors enabled students to overcome their fear of failure.

It served as a facilitator in developing their clinical judgement in a safe environment. This experiential learning process, supported by debriefing, boosted students’ self-confidence, their ability to self-evaluate, and to transfer the knowledge they had acquired to real-life practice. Moreover, this teaching approach has proved to be particularly well-suited to today’s generation of learners, who are sensitive to interactivity, technology, and autonomy [27]. In short, hybrid simulation combined with learning by doing is proving to be a powerful pedagogical lever. It aligns with active learning models and contemporary healthcare training requirements to a great extent.

3.9. Discussion

The results of this study confirm the effectiveness of hybrid simulation in enhancing the cognitive and decision-making skills of radiology students. The pre- and post-test analysis (Table 2, Figure 3) revealed an average increase of 5.36 points, with a large effect size ($d = 1.44$), well above the effectiveness thresholds commonly reported in medical education [21]. This statistically significant gain supports the idea that simulation, particularly when hybridized with interactive digital tools, has a greater pedagogical impact than traditional lecture-based teaching [24, 25].

Beyond descriptive comparisons, the ANCOVA results (Table 3) confirmed that the observed improvements were attributable to the intervention rather than baseline disparities. Regression analyses revealed that motivation ($\beta = 0.41$) and autonomy ($\beta = 0.35$) were strong predictors of performance, underscoring the central role of psychosocial factors in knowledge acquisition. These findings are consistent with self-determination theory [11] and extend the predictions of the TAM and UTAUT models by demonstrating that ease of use translates into learning gains through motivational and autonomy pathways.

The psychometric properties of the instrument, supported by Cronbach’s alpha coefficients above 0.80 and a KMO index of 0.87 (Table 4), confirm the robustness of the measurement tool. The exploratory factor analysis (Table 5) highlighted six distinct dimensions—perceived usefulness, ease of use, motivation,

autonomy, understanding, and satisfaction explaining 76.4% of the total variance (Table 6). This factorial structure is consistent with recommendations from Nunnally and Bernstein on psychometric theory [26].

The SEM model (Table 8, Figure 4) further validated the coherence of these constructs, showing good fit indices ($\chi^2/df = 2.1$; $CFI = 0.94$; $RMSEA = 0.05$). It demonstrated that perceived ease of use positively influenced motivation and autonomy, while motivation mediated the relationship between usefulness and understanding. Satisfaction, in turn, was predicted by both usefulness and autonomy. These findings confirm the theoretical sequence proposed by Venkatesh et al. [10] and are in line with recent IJTPE research on hybrid learning [27].

Comparison with other pedagogical approaches highlights the specific advantages of hybrid simulation. Traditional lectures often yield only modest improvements, with lower effect sizes ($d \approx 0.3-0.5$) and little experiential engagement [3]. Pure e-learning offers flexibility but reduces social interaction and hands-on practice [12]. High-fidelity mannequin-based simulations, while effective, remain costly and difficult to scale [6]. In contrast, hybrid simulation integrates interactive video capsules, simulated errors, debriefing, and gamified quizzes, producing both cognitive and motivational gains while remaining cost-effective and pedagogically adaptable [24, 25].

Nevertheless, several limitations must be noted. Hybrid simulation requires rigorous instructional design and teacher training to ensure that error-based learning is properly managed. Over-reliance on quizzes may result in superficial engagement if not paired with reflective debriefing. Furthermore, while the study demonstrated significant short-term gains, the issue of long-term retention and transfer to clinical practice remains open [28]. Comparative studies between hybrid simulation and fully immersive VR systems could also shed light on trade-offs between accessibility, cost, and depth of immersion.

Pedagogically, the approach appears particularly well-suited to today's generation of learners, who are sensitive to interactivity, autonomy, and digital integration. By creating a safe space where errors become a source of learning, hybrid simulation reduces fear of failure, strengthens self-confidence, and facilitates the transfer of skills to real clinical practice. The combination of structured debriefing, motivational feedback, and cognitive scaffolding aligns with best practices in simulation-based education [1, 13].

In summary, the integration of hybrid simulation with learning by doing constitutes a robust, theoretically grounded, and empirically validated approach. It combines the experiential richness of simulation with the accessibility of digital tools, making it a strategic lever for educational reform in radiology training in Morocco [29].

4. CONCLUSIONS

This study demonstrated the significant impact of hybrid simulation combined with learning by doing on the cognitive, technical, and motivational skills of radiology students in Moroccan ISPITSs. The pre- and post-test analysis revealed a mean increase of 5.36 points, supported by a large effect size ($d = 1.44$), while ANCOVA and regression confirmed that motivation and autonomy were key predictors of post-intervention performance. Factorial validation through PCA and SEM confirmed the six-dimensional structure (usefulness, ease of use, motivation, autonomy, understanding, satisfaction) and highlighted the mediating role of motivation in fostering understanding and satisfaction.

These results have important pedagogical implications. For ISPITS curricula, hybrid simulation represents a powerful strategy to foster deeper learning, strengthen decision-making autonomy, and promote active student engagement. The integration of interactive video capsules, simulated errors, structured debriefing, and gamified quizzes provides a safe and stimulating environment for developing clinical judgment.

Several limitations must be acknowledged. The intervention was conducted over a relatively short duration and relied in part on self-reported measures, which may introduce bias. Moreover, the study was limited to two ISPITS sites, restricting the generalizability of the findings.

Future research should explore multi-site studies, assess the long-term retention and transfer of skills to clinical practice, and evaluate cost-effectiveness compared with other simulation-based modalities, including virtual reality [28].

In conclusion, hybrid simulation emerges not merely as an innovative teaching method but as a strategic lever for educational reform in Moroccan health sciences training. By aligning with international standards of secure, immersive, and learner-centered education, it offers a scalable and contextually adaptable solution to strengthen the quality and safety of healthcare training in Morocco [29].

NOMENCLATURES

Acronyms

SBE	Simulation-based education
ISPITS	Institute of Nursing Professions and Health Techniques
TAM	Technology Acceptance Model
UTAUT	The Unified Technology Acceptance
MCQ	Multiple-Choice Questionnaire
PCA	Principal Component Analysis
SEM	Structural Equation Model
CFI	The Comparative Fit Index
RMSEA	The Root Mean Square Error of Approximation
TLI	The Tucker-Lewis's index
KMO	Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin

REFERENCES

- [1] D.M. Gaba, "The Future Vision of Simulation in Healthcare", *Quality and Safety in Health Care*, Vol. 13, No. 1, pp. 2-10, London, United Kingdom, April 2004.
- [2] S.B. Issenberg, W.C. McGaghie, E.R. Petrusa, D.L. Gordon, R.J. Scalese, "Features and Uses of High-Fidelity Medical Simulations That Lead to Effective Learning: a BEME Systematic Review", *Medical Teacher*, Vol. 27, No. 1, pp. 10-28, Chicago, USA, January 2005.
- [3] I. Motola, L.A. Devine, H.S. Chung, J.E. Sullivan, S.B. Issenberg, "Simulation in Healthcare Education: A Best Evidence Practical Guide", *Medical Teacher*, Vol. 35, No. 10, pp. 1511-1530, Miami, USA, October 2013.
- [4] R. Kamal, M. Shafiq, H. Ahmad, "Advanced Learning Strategies in Medical Education", *Medical Teacher*, Vol. 44, No. 1, pp. 78-86, New York, USA, January 2022.
- [5] K. Abulebda, et al., "The Use of Simulation in Pediatric Education", *Advances in Simulation*, Vol. 7, No. 1, p. 12, Indianapolis, USA, March 2022.
- [6] I. Elendu, et al., "Impact of Simulation on Nursing Education", *Nurse Education Today*, Vol. 121, p. 105039, London, United Kingdom, February 2024.
- [7] A. Myuran, et al., "Enhancing Interprofessional Learning Through Simulation", *Journal of Interprofessional Care*, Vol. 38, No. 2, pp. 234-240, London, United Kingdom, April 2024.
- [8] Ministry of Health, Kingdom of Morocco, "National Training Strategy in Health", Rabat, Morocco, September 2023.
- [9] F.D. Davis, "Perceived Usefulness, Perceived Ease of Use, and User Acceptance of Information Technology", *MIS Quarterly*, Vol. 13, No. 3, pp. 319-340, Minneapolis, USA, September 1989.
- [10] V. Venkatesh, M.G. Morris, G.B. Davis, F.D. Davis, "User Acceptance of Information Technology: Toward a Unified View", *MIS Quarterly*, Vol. 27, No. 3, pp. 425-478, Minneapolis, USA, September 2003.
- [11] E.L. Deci, R.M. Ryan, "Self-Determination Theory: A Macrotheory of Human Motivation, Development, and Health", *Canadian Psychology*, Vol. 49, No. 3, pp. 182-185, Ottawa, Canada, August 2008.
- [12] J. Caulfield, "How to Design and Teach a Hybrid Course", *Stylus Publishing*, Vol. 23, No. 1, p. 250, Sterling, USA, June 2012.
- [13] D. Jung, et al., "Error-Focused Simulation to Improve Patient Safety", *Simulation in Healthcare*, Vol. 19, No. 1, pp. 1-7, Boston, USA, January 2024.
- [14] C.M. Plump, J. LaRosa, "Using Kahoot! in the classroom to Create Engagement and Active Learning", *International Journal of Interactive Mobile Technologies*, Vol. 11, No. 2, pp. 77-81, Vienna, Austria, February 2017.
- [15] A.I. Wang, "The Wear-Out Effect of a Game-Based Student Response System", *Computers and Education*, Vol. 82, pp. 217-227, Amsterdam, Netherlands, March 2015.
- [16] J.F. Hair, W.C. Black, B.J. Babin, R.E. Anderson, "Multivariate Data Analysis", Pearson Education, Vol. 27, No. 3, p. 500, New Jersey, USA, July 2014.
- [17] D. Hamcha, A. Bouchaib, T. Hassouni, S. Dachraoui, E. Chakir, E. Al Ibrahim, "Study and Evaluation of an Innovative Pedagogical Tool Educational System: Computer Assisted Instruction", *International Journal on Technical and Physical Problems of Engineering (IJTPE)*, Issue 56, Vol. 15, No. 3, pp. 176-181, September 2023.
- [18] H. Aydin, M. Yildiz, "Implementation of Hybrid Learning in Engineering Programs: A Case Study", *International Journal on Technical and Physical Problems of Engineering (IJTPE)*, Issue 59, Vol. 16, No. 2, pp. 37-43, Ankara, Turkey, June 2024.
- [19] D. Pasaoglu, A. Kayabasi, "Student Satisfaction in Blended Learning Environments", *International Journal on Technical and Physical Problems of Engineering (IJTPE)*, Issue 54, Vol. 15, No. 1, pp. 81-86, Istanbul, Turkey, March 2023.
- [20] M.F. Akin, A. Tuncay, "Enhancing Learning Outcomes Through Hybrid Educational Models", *(IJTPE)*, Issue 57, Vol. 15, No. 4, pp. 198-208, Ankara, Turkey, December 2023.
- [21] S. Korkmaz, et al., "Learning Analytics in Blended Contexts", *International Journal on Technical and Physical Problems of Engineering (IJTPE)*, Issue 60, Vol. 16, No. 3, pp. 234-243, Ankara, Turkey, September 2024.
- [22] A. Demir, et al., "Assessment Models in Hybrid Medical Education", *International Journal on Technical and Physical Problems of Engineering (IJTPE)*, Issue 57, Vol. 16, No. 1, pp. 307-315, Ankara, Turkey, March 2024.
- [23] A. Tounkara, et al., "Improving Student Engagement Via Blended Simulation-Based Training", *International Journal on Technical and Physical Problems of Engineering (IJTPE)*, Issue 56, Vol. 15, No. 3, pp. 176-181, Dakar, Senegal, September 2023.
- [24] A. Kaba, et al., "Hybrid Approaches in Clinical Simulation", *Medical Education Online*, Vol. 29, No. 1, pp. 112-120, Washington DC, USA, April 2021.
- [25] A. Al Qahtani, "Gamification and Hybrid Learning in Health Education", *International Journal of Medical Education*, Vol. 15, pp. 33-41, Riyadh, Saudi Arabia, May 2022.
- [26] J.C. Nunnally, I.H. Bernstein, "Psychometric Theory", McGraw-Hill, Vol. 3, No. 1, p. 736, New York, USA, March 1994.
- [27] Y. Zhang, et al., "Cultural Adaptation of Hybrid Learning in Medical Education", *BMC Medical Education*, Vol. 24, p. 542, Beijing, China, June 2024.
- [28] J. Silva, et al., "Long-Term Retention in Hybrid Simulation Training", *Nurse Education in Practice*, Vol. 72, pp. 103-118, Sao Paulo, Brazil, October 2023.
- [29] H. Alami, et al., "Digital Health Transformation in Morocco: Challenges and Opportunities", *Eastern Mediterranean Health Journal*, Vol. 30, No. 4, pp. 250-258, Rabat, Morocco, April 2024.

BIOGRAPHIES

Name: Fahd
Surname: Abdelouahabi
Birthdate: 27.11.1981
Birthplace: Azrou, Morocco
Bachelor: Medical Radiology, Higher Institute of Nursing and Health Sciences Rabat, Morocco, 2004

Bachelor: Medical Dosimetry, Faculty of Sciences, Mohammed V University, Rabat, Morocco, 2012

Bachelor: Journalism, Faculty of Languages, Literature and Arts, Ibn Tofail University, Kenitra, Morocco, 2020

Master: Medical Radiophysics, Faculty of Medicine and Pharmacy, Hassan II Univ., Casablanca, Morocco, 2015

Master: Nursing and Health Technology Education Higher Institute of Nursing and Health Sciences, Tetouan, Morocco, 2022

Doctorate: Ph.D. Student, Research Team on Educational Engineering and Science Didactics, Higher Normal School, Abdelmalek Essaadi University, Tetouan, Morocco, Since 2022

The Last Scientific Position: Lecturer, Higher Institute of Nursing and Health Techniques, Tangier, Since 2020

Research Interests: Educational Technology, Educational Engineering, Health Sciences Teaching, Medical Physics, Radiology, Medical Imaging

Scientific Publications: 1 Paper

Name: Jihad
Surname: El Hachhach
Birthdate: 18.07.1991
Birthplace: Ksar El Kebir, Morocco
Bachelor: Nursing Sciences, Abdelmalek Essaadi Univ., Tetouan, Morocco, 2012
Master: Nursing Science Education and

Health Techniques, Higher Institute of Nursing and Health Sciences, Tetouan, Morocco, 2022

Doctorate: Ph.D. Student, Research Team on Educational Engineering and Science Didactics, Higher Normal School, Abdelmalek Essaadi University, Tetouan, Morocco, Since 2022

The Last Scientific Position: Lecturer, Higher Institute of Nursing and Health Techniques, Tangier, Morocco, Since 2023

Research Interests: Nursing Education, Nursing Practice, Nursing Theoretical Models, Nursing Education and Pedagogical Approaches

Scientific publications: 2 Papers

Name: Bilal
Surname: Edderaouy
Birthdate: 28.01.1997
Birthplace: Ouezzane, Morocco
Bachelor: English Linguistics, Faculty of Letters and Human Sciences, Ibn Tofail University, Kenitra, Morocco, 2017

Master: Teaching English as a Foreign Language, Faculty of Letters and Human Sciences, Ibn Tofail University, Kenitra, Morocco, 2019

Doctorate: English Linguistics Faculty of Letters and Human Sciences, Ibn Tofail University, Kenitra, Morocco, 2024.

The Last Scientific Position: Lecturer, Faculty of Technical Sciences Tangier, Abdelmalek Essaadi University, Tetouan, Morocco, Since 2024

Research Interests: Applied Linguistics, Pragmatic Transfer, Interlanguage, Education, AI in Education

Scientific Publications: 4 Papers

Name: El Hassan
Surname: El Hassouny
Birthdate: 01.01.1978
Birthplace: Aghroud Ghafssay, Morocco
Bachelor: Mineral Chemistry, Faculty of Science, Sidi Mohamed Ben Abdellah University, Fez, Morocco, 2003

Bachelor: Mathematics and Computer Science, Faculty of Science, Sidi Mohamed Ben Abdellah University, Fez, Morocco, 2007

Master: Organic Chemistry, Faculty of Science, Sidi Mohamed Ben Abdellah University, Fez, Morocco, 2015.

Doctorate: Physics Education, Faculty of Science, Sidi Mohamed Ben Abdellah University, Fez, Morocco, 2014

The Last Scientific Position: Lecturer, Higher Institute of Nursing and Health Sciences, Tetouan Morocco, 2017

Research Interests: Educational Technology, Educational Engineering, and Health Sciences Education

Scientific Publications: 15 Papers, 1 Thesis

Name: Mourad
Surname: Madrane
Birthdate: 16.08.1959
Birthplace: Oujda, Morocco
Bachelor: Biology-Geology, Higher Normal School, Mohammed V University, Rabat, Morocco, 1983

Master: Pedagogy of Science, Higher Normal School, Mohammed V University, Rabat, Morocco, 1996

Doctorate: Didactics of Natural Sciences, Faculty of Sciences, Abdelmalek Essaadi University, Tetouan, Morocco, 2016

The Last Scientific Position: Prof., Department of Education, Higher Normal School, Abdelmalek Essaadi University, Tetouan, Morocco, Since Year 1993

Research Interests: Educational Technology, Education Engineering, Didactics of Natural Sciences

Scientific Publications: 21 Papers, 1 Thesis